

EU CHIP CHRONICLES

**Building Europe's
Semiconductor
Talent Ecosystem**

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ISSUE

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Foreword

Welcome to the fifth issue of the **EU Chip Chronicles**, our magazine dedicated to the people, projects, and policies shaping Europe's semiconductor future.

As the momentum around the EU Chips Act continues to grow, with it comes the recognition that our success depends not only on cutting-edge technologies, but also on the networks of talent, collaboration, and trust we build together.

In these pages, you will meet inspiring voices from across the ecosystem. From Romane Léauté's and Hannu-Matti Järvinen's insights on the RESCHIP4EU project, to Bernie Capraro's reflections on the evolving skills landscape, to Christina Schindler's perspective on Europe's unique chip strengths, we highlight the people driving change. We also showcase the aCCcess project, which is laying the foundations for competence centres that will nurture tomorrow's semiconductor workforce.

Beyond interviews with key players in the chip skills ecosystem, we bring you timely reports: one on AI's growing role in future-proofing the chip sector, and another tackling the power-performance conundrum: critical knowledge for those navigating today's fast-moving markets.

Finally, our events section takes you straight to the heart of the action, with a spotlight on the upcoming Industrial Alliance workshop, SEMICON Europa, and EF ECS 2025; moments where ideas become strategies, and strategies become impact.

At Chip Chronicles, our mission is to capture not just the headlines, but the collective effort driving Europe forward in semiconductors. I hope this issue sparks ideas, informs your work, and strengthens the connections that will carry us all towards Europe's ambition of technological resilience and sovereignty.

Enjoy the read,

Silvana Muscella

ALLPROS.eu Technical Coordinator

📱 Reskill, Upskill, and Train: RESCHIP4EU Builds Europe's Future Chip Workforce

✍️ Author: Roberta Fabrizi

Europe's semiconductor ecosystem faces a pressing challenge: a shortage of skilled engineers able to bridge the gap between hardware design and software development in embedded systems. The **RESCHIP4EU** project, coordinated by **EIT Digital**, is stepping up to address this need through an ambitious programme of education and training that combines academic excellence with strong industry collaboration.

*"At its core, RESCHIP4EU aims to train, upskill, and reskill the workforce of tomorrow in embedded systems and chip design," explains **Romane Léauté**, Project Coordinator at EIT Digital. "We want to ensure that future engineers master both the hardware and the software components that define today's microelectronics."*

A dual-track approach: Masters and online learning

The flagship of RESCHIP4EU is a **two-year Master degree in Embedded Systems Design**, co-developed by nine higher education institutions across five countries, together with industrial partners including **STMicroelectronics** and **SEMI Europe**.

The programme requires mobility: students spend their first year at one university and their second year at another in a different country, graduating with two diplomas. *"This mobility is a core element of the programme,"* says Léauté. *"It ensures students are exposed to different cultures, academic traditions, and industrial ecosystems, which enriches their learning."*

In parallel, the consortium is preparing a series of **online courses**, set to launch in autumn 2025. These modules will provide flexible learning opportunities for both students and professionals seeking to gain the necessary hard skills essential for a career in the sector. Certificates will be jointly awarded by **EIT Digital** and the universities delivering the courses.

Where students can study embedded systems design (Credit: EIT Digital)

Linking industry and academia

For **Professor Hannu-Matti Järvinen** (Tampere University), who leads the curriculum design, the project's uniqueness lies in bridging the often-siloed worlds of hardware and software. "Chips don't function without software," he stresses. "Our aim is to train engineers who can operate across this continuum and that are able to design systems where hardware and software are developed together."

The recently published [market analysis and curriculum design report](#), other than highlighting how skill needs differ across Europe, is a prime example of how collaboration between industry and academia is of essence to have

a clear, and most importantly, timely picture of the skills required by an ever evolving job market. RESCHIP4EU's flexible, multi-country structure allows it to respond to regional differences and mutable needs while still building a strong, shared European foundation.

Looking ahead

The project is preparing to welcome its **first cohort of students in autumn 2025**, marking a major milestone. At the same time, the launch of its online courses will extend its reach far beyond the classroom. Importantly, RESCHIP4EU also integrates **entrepreneurship and innovation training**, ensuring that graduates not only become excellent engineers but also future leaders capable of driving Europe's chip industry forward.

As **Léauté** concludes, this project extends beyond the need of training new students. It's about shaping a resilient and innovative semiconductor workforce for Europe, one that meets the ambitions of the **EU Chips Act** and strengthens our technological sovereignty.

For further information on the project, feel free to consult the [RESCHIP4EU project page](#).

Building Europe's Semiconductor Talent Pool: A Conversation with Bernie Capraro

✍ Author: Roberta Fabrizi

Bernie Capraro has spent his entire working life in semiconductors. His fascination with the industry began in 1987, during an Erasmus exchange in Germany, when he stepped into a fabrication plant for the first time.

"It was at that point I decided, well, this is what I think I'd like to do for my career," he recalls.

Two internships, a final-year project, and a master's degree later, he began working in photonics—what he describes as *"basically helping build the Internet."* His career took him from Telefunken to Nortel, Applied Materials and Newport Wafer Fab, before he eventually relocated with his family to Ireland to join Intel.

Capraro would stay at Intel for 27 years, working as a fab engineer, process and equipment manager, and later in R&D. There, he discovered a passion for building networks with universities and research institutions. Perhaps most importantly, he became deeply engaged in one of the industry's most pressing challenges: **cultivating a sustainable pipeline of talent.**

From Intel to SEMI Europe: A Lifelong Focus on Skills

At Intel, Capraro found himself on the frontlines of talent development. When Intel's FAB 34 in Leixlip required 1,600 skilled employees, he led efforts to collaborate with universities to deliver the workforce. *"With a five-million population in Ireland, it was a competitive job market,"* he explains. *"But through strategic programmes with key universities, it was done."*

Now retired from Intel, Capraro has carried this mission into his current role at **SEMI Europe**, where he focuses on mobilising talent across the continent. His task is no small one: ensuring Europe has the skills base to meet the ambitious targets laid out in the EU Chips Act and reducing reliance on global supply chains.

Can Europe Reach Its Chips Act Targets?

The EU has set a goal of producing **20% of the world's semiconductors by 2030**. Capraro is cautiously optimistic, though realistic about the hurdles ahead.

"Well, if we've got total blue sky and say yes, we're going to reach these targets by 2030, then no, we don't have the talent pool by 2030," he says. *"But I think we have a little bit more time than that. The industry goes in cycles, and while we're in a down period now, the aim is still the same. It may just take a bit longer."*

Still, for him, the **urgency lies** not in the deadlines but in **education**. "The thing that concerns me the most is the T and the E in STEM education. It's a little bit

weak for my liking. We need to start in the schools, with teachers better prepared to show students what today's world of work looks like."

Tackling Diversity Head-On

One recurring challenge is the underrepresentation of women. Capraro describes a technician training programme in Ireland where mixed classes would often lose their only female participants before completion. The environment was maybe not welcoming.

The solution? An all-female programme. *"All 16 women graduated and were hired into technician roles in one go,"* he says. *"It showed that the environment matters. If we're serious about diversity, we need to tackle these issues honestly and directly."*

For Capraro, this is not simply about fairness. It's about necessity. Europe cannot afford to exclude half its potential talent pool at a time when demand for skilled workers is exploding.

Bridging the Skills Mismatch

Across Europe, a skills mismatch looms large. While thousands of students graduate each year, many lack the specific competencies needed for careers in the semiconductor industry.

Capraro believes two things are key to addressing this: improving the image of the industry, and **widening the talent pool**.

"Not enough people know about us. I didn't either back in 1987, but today, students need to see that this is a cool industry to work in"

He points to initiatives like Ireland's STEM Teacher Internship Programme, which places trainee teachers in tech companies for summer internships. *"When they go back to the classroom, they've seen first-hand what a career in tech looks like. That has a huge impact."*

At the same time, the industry must open its doors to **more diverse disciplines**. *"Do all semiconductor engineers need to be electrical or mechanical*

engineers? No," he argues. *"We hire chemists, and why not biologists too? They do experiments, gather and analyse data, and draw conclusions. Those are exactly the skills sustaining engineers need in fabs today."*

By encouraging students from chemistry, biology, and data science backgrounds and by offering **micro-credentials** to bridge gaps Capraro sees a chance to build a broader, more diverse workforce.

"I'm a firm believer that micro-credentials not only offer reskilling and upskilling, but they should be pushed back into undergraduate degrees as elective courses" he says. For example, biology students could take a semester-long module on semiconductor process technology, giving them industry-ready knowledge before graduation.

Stocking the talent pool

When asked about success stories, he cites Ireland's Human Capital Initiative as a powerful model: **government funding and industry collaboration**

created new training programmes, including master's-level modules in Python, data analytics, and applied AI for process engineers.

"That collaboration between industry and academia was key. For example, it gave engineers the tools to use AI to monitor thousands of control charts in fabs, something that was becoming extremely difficult and time consuming to do manually."

For Capraro, Europe needs more of **these triple-helix collaborations** amongst government, academia, and industry. *"What I'd like to see now is a second version, to keep it going. These skills should trickle down into undergrad programmes so graduates arrive with the basics already in place."*

Bernie uses a fisherman's metaphor to describe Europe's talent challenge. *"At the start of the season, the fishing club members all pay their fees. That*

money goes to maintaining the lake and stocking it with fish. Then, when the season starts, the fun begins: everyone competes to catch the best fish."

In the same way, he argues, **Europe needs to collaborate up front to "stock the pool"** with skilled graduates. *"The competition should come later, when companies are hiring. But building the talent pool must be a shared responsibility."*

A Career of Impact

When asked about his inspirations, Capraro doesn't point to a single mentor or leader. Instead, he reflects on his own career and his drive to have an impact in the world.

"I started as an intern in 1987 when there was no easy access to the Internet, no home PCs, no smartphones, no AI. Today, all of those things exist—and they stem from what we did in the semiconductor industry. I'm very proud of that," he says.

"Students coming into this industry can have a huge impact, often without realising it. Semiconductors have made the world a better place for most people. There's still a long way to go, but that means there's opportunity for the next generation."

Looking Ahead

Europe's semiconductor future will depend not only on fabs and funding, but on people. If the continent is to reach (or even approach) the **Chips Act** target of 20% global market share, it must rethink how it educates, trains, and inspires its young people.

For Capraro, the message is clear: *"Without talent, none of this is possible. But with the right collaboration, the right image, and the right training, Europe can build a talent pool big enough to compete."*

It's a vision rooted not in pessimism, but in decades of experience - and in the belief that the next generation, if given the chance, can make as much and more of an impact on the world as he has.

Chips of Europe - Interview with Christina Schindler

 Author: Valeriya Fetisova

Chips of Europe: Bringing the Semiconductor World to the Next Generation

"If you think of the number of transistors on an AI chip, this is equal to the number of stars in our galaxy. That's just amazing to deal with such small, tiny devices, create them, and make them work."

For **Kristina Schindler**, Professor for Microsystem Technology at Munich University of Applied Sciences, this is what makes semiconductors truly exciting. However, she knows that this fascination often doesn't reach students early enough. That's where the Chips of Europe project comes in.

"It's all about making semiconductors more visible and the programmes more attractive for educating future talents," explains Kristina Schindler, who coordinates the project.

What is Chips of Europe?

Chips of Europe (Creating Higher-Education Industry Programmes for the Semiconductor Industry of Europe) is an ambitious initiative to make semiconductor education more attractive, visible, and aligned with industry needs.

The project operates on multiple fronts:

- In **schools**, it works with teachers and secondary students to spark curiosity about semiconductors at an early stage.
- In **universities**, it supports programmes improvement to match industry expectations, ensuring graduates are ready for real-world challenges.
- With **industry**, it facilitates a direct pipeline between education and employment, so that Europe can enhance its own semiconductor talent pool.

Learning by Playing: The Power of Virtual

One of Chips of Europe's most innovative tools is the creation of **virtual labs**, aimed to be accessible to anyone and anywhere.

"You learn best if you can play with something and make mistakes," Kristina Schindler says. *"As semiconductor technology is super expensive, it's hard for us to make our students play with the real machines."*

Through **digital twins of real lab tools**, students can experiment, test parameters, and learn at their own pace, all through a simple browser application.

"We do not want to replace teaching in presence," she clarifies. *"But we want every student to get access to a lab, try out different processes, and get more insight into real fabrication."*

Addressing the Skills Gap

The project tackles one of Europe’s most pressing challenges in the semiconductor industry: the **skills gap**. But this work isn’t without hurdles.

“The major challenge schools face is the tight schedule they have,” Kristina Schindler explains. “Typically only physics is taught, and semiconductors are just a small part of that. It’s really hard for us to find a slot in the schedule of normal secondary schools.”

Time is also a challenge for universities, where semiconductor education often competes with research priorities and teaching loads.

Building Bridges: Industry and Academia

Kristina Schindler believes that **investing in education is essential for Europe’s semiconductor future**.

“It’s very important to continue supporting projects not only for research but also for education. This is how we can fascinate our students,” she says.

To ensure students are job-ready, Chips of Europe promotes close **collaboration with industry**. This includes advisory boards, guest lectures, internships, and even industry-led courses.

“If students see what kind of great jobs are out there, what career paths they can take, and work on real applications, that’s how we fascinate them for this field,” she emphasizes.

A Tiny World Where You Can Make a Huge Impact

For Kristina Schindler, semiconductors aren’t just a field of study. They’re the hidden engine behind modern life.

“Semiconductors are in every daily-life application. They’re the really small things that make our lives great,” she says.

Through Chips of Europe, Kristina Schindler hopes to share that sense of wonder with a new generation and equip them to shape the future of one of Europe’s most critical industries.

aCCcess: Building Europe's Semiconductor Competence Network

 Author: Roberta Fabrizi

Strengthening Europe's semiconductor industry, means tackling multiple challenges at once. From attracting talent to reskilling, from building new infrastructures to scaling production capacity, a diversified and holistic approach is needed.

Looking in more detail into capacity building in the semiconductor pipeline, there is a need to consolidate highly requested skills on a local level, while also creating an ecosystem where knowledge, design, training and innovation can circulate seamlessly across borders. This is precisely the mission of

aCCcess, a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) that is structuring and moderating the network of semiconductor competence centres under the [EU Chips Act](#).

"We define ourselves as ecosystem designers," explains **Régis Hamelin**, CTO of Blumorpho and coordinator of aCCcess. *"The project's vision is to connect the national competence centres that are emerging across Europe, and ensure that, together, they form a vibrant and synergistic network to support talent, startups, and innovators."*

Competence Centres at the Heart of the Chips Act

The **EU Chips Act** foresees one competence centre per Member State, acting as a hub where companies—especially SMEs and startups—can access technical expertise, training, consultancy, and even funding guidance. Some countries, like Belgium or Spain, have opted for two centres, reflecting different technological strengths such as photonics.

“These centres are highly diverse,” notes Hamelin. *“Germany, France, or the Netherlands already have well-structured ecosystems. Other countries, like Slovakia or Lithuania, are just beginning to build their capabilities. Our job in aCCcess is to coordinate, encourage synergies, and help ensure that no country is left behind.”*

Map of competence centres across the EU (Credit: aCCcess project)

Five Focus Groups for Collaboration

To make the network operational and sustainable, aCCcess has created **five focus groups**:

- 📁 **Operations & Best Practices** – addressing daily activities, business models, and collaboration schemes.
- 📁 **Outreach & Events** – amplifying communication and awareness across Europe.
- 📁 **Technology Offer** – building a catalogue of the capabilities and services available in each competence centre.
- 📁 **Training and Skills development** – mapping existing education opportunities and developing proposals for micro-credentials and European-level curricula.
- 📁 **Access to Finance** – establishing links to venture capital, investors, and instruments.

A flagship initiative in this last area is the [Chips Venture Forum](#), organised alongside SEMICON Europa. This event will bring together startups, investors, corporate entities, and EU institutions for a day of pitching, networking, and strategy discussions on how to scale European semiconductor startups.

Success: Collaboration, Startups, and Design

For Hamelin, success in aCCcess will mean demonstrating **real cross-border collaboration**, not just on paper but in practice. *“If in four years we can point to startups that grew and scaled thanks to support from the network, that would be a real achievement,”* he says.

He also stresses the importance of **promoting design capabilities** in Europe. *“Many SMEs today rely only on off-the-shelf components. But by developing their own ASICs or MEMS, companies can create far more value. We want competence centres to help make design more accessible and affordable, and to encourage new fabless companies to emerge in Europe.”*

Looking Ahead

With 30 competence centres already selected across Europe, the network is still in its early stages, having to align national and EU funding contracts, but aCCcess is steadily building momentum. Over the coming years, it will be instrumental in shaping how Europe’s semiconductor ecosystem develops, ensuring that startups and SMEs have access not only to facilities and funding, but also to knowledge, skills, and strategic support.

As Hamelin concludes: *“Our ambition is to stimulate the emergence of future European champions in semiconductors. By creating a connected and collaborative network, we are laying the foundations for sovereignty, competitiveness, and long-term growth.”*

Project Partners

The **aCCcess** consortium brings together seven partners with complementary expertise:

- 📁 **Blumorpho** – Coordinator
- 📁 VDI/VDE Innovation + Technik GmbH
- 📁 Minalogic
- 📁 Silicon Saxony
- 📁 Silicon Alps
- 📁 Mesap
- 📁 Czech National Semiconductor Cluster

To learn more about the project, consult their webpage [here](#).

ALLPROS.eu Reports

AI in the chips sector: Future-proofing the EU's semiconductor industry

 Author: Matilde Serrau

Artificial intelligence is reshaping the semiconductor supply chain, offering transformative opportunities in manufacturing, logistics, and design. As AI becomes an integral part of chip manufacturing, the industry faces complex challenges while maximising its technological and economic potential. AI-driven chip design leverages machine learning and generative AI to improve design, verification, and testing processes. From digitising manufacturing to optimising chip performance and energy use, AI also contributes to environmental sustainability by reducing resource consumption and identifying safer materials.

However, major barriers hinder widespread adoption, including talent shortages, fragmented data ecosystems, and access difficulties for SMEs. Open innovation (OI) is a key enabler in this context, helping companies, especially SMEs, adapt faster to technological change. Open source software (OSS) foundations offer open platforms and safe spaces for companies and competitors to collaborate on shared standards and components, overcoming resistance to AI through co-creation, transparency, and legal clarity. Larger companies can balance in-house development and external providers, but SMEs often lack such resources, making OSS a strategic asset for competitiveness.

To unlock AI's full impact, the industry must promote open innovation models, invest in upskilling, and build inclusive ecosystems that empower SMEs. With targeted support and investment, the EU can enhance the competitiveness, resilience, and sustainability of its semiconductor sector in a fast-evolving landscape.

Read more on Zenodo:

<https://zenodo.org/records/15630494>

POLICY BRIEF

AI in the chips sector:
Future-proofing the EU's
semiconductor industry

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The power performance conundrum: insights from our last market trend webinar

 Author: Luis Fernandes

AI workloads are driving unprecedented power consumption, straining existing datacentre systems. As priorities shift toward sustainability and efficiency, datacentres face mounting challenges in balancing performance, energy demands, and environmental goals amidst this transformative era.

Modern datacentres face inefficiencies with air cooling, struggling to manage escalating power densities from AI workloads. As systems exceed thermal limits, alternative solutions like liquid cooling become essential to ensure operational reliability and energy efficiency.

Liquid cooling outperforms air cooling by efficiently managing high power densities and reducing thermal stress. It enables datacentres to handle AI-driven workloads while lowering energy consumption and improving sustainability. Direct-to-chip cooling suits large-scale deployments, while immersion cooling offers unmatched efficiency for edge systems. Liquid cooling is pivotal in addressing power and thermal challenges.

By adopting liquid cooling to tackle high-density power demands, training skilled professionals for deployment and maintenance, and pushing for legislative frameworks to standardize sustainable datacentre operations, stakeholders can achieve long-term energy efficiency and environmental impact reduction.

Innovation and collaboration are essential to overcoming power challenges. By embracing advanced cooling technologies and sustainable practices, the industry can pave the way for efficient, future-ready datacentres.

Read more on Zenodo:

<https://zenodo.org/records/15270611>

Event Highlights: Shaping Europe's Semiconductor Future

This autumn will see a series of major gatherings for Europe's semiconductor ecosystem, bringing stakeholders together to exchange insights, showcase innovation, and strengthen collaboration.

From Insights to Impact: Advancing Europe's Semiconductor Ambitions

On **13 November in Brussels**, the Alliance's **three Working Groups** will convene for their second joint workshop. The event will focus on turning shared expertise into actionable strategies to bolster Europe's sustainability, supply chain resilience, and skills pipeline.

SEMICON Europa 2025

From **18-21 November in Munich**, **SEMICON Europa**, co-located with productronica, will bring industry leaders, innovators, and policymakers together under the theme Global Collaborations for European Economic Resilience. ALLPROS will be present to highlight Europe's strategic role in fostering sustainable and secure semiconductor value chains.

[More info](#)

EF ECS 2025

Rounding off the season, **EF ECS** will take place in **Malta on 3-4 December**. This international forum offers a platform to connect across the entire Electronic Components and Systems value chain, with a strong focus on research, innovation, and collaborative opportunities to advance Europe's semiconductor ambitions. [More info](#)

Together, these events mark a pivotal moment for Europe's semiconductor community to align efforts, build resilience, and shape the future of the industry.

The EU Chips Chronicles is the quarterly magazine of the ALLPROS.eu project showcasing views and exemplary stories from across the European semiconductor community.

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